

A Cross Sectional Study to Assess the Incidence of Aerobic and Fungal Infection in Post-Operative Wound Infection

Anupama Singh¹, Ranjit Kumar Singh²

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Microbiology, Netaji Subhas Medical College and Hospital, Bihta, Patna, Bihar, India.

²Associate Professor, Department of Orthopaedics, Nalanda medical college and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

Received: 25-10-2022 / Revised: 28-11-2022 / Accepted: 02-01-2023

Corresponding author: Dr. Ranjit Kumar Singh

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Aim: The aim of the study was to isolate aerobic bacterial and fungal infections from post-operative wounds.

Methods: The study was a cross sectional study which was carried in the Department of Microbiology, Netaji Subhas Medical College and Hospital, Bihta, Bihar, India for one year. Out of 210 samples, 100 samples were culture positive (47.61%). Total 100 patients with post-operative wound infection either sex or any age, who had surgical wound pus, discharge, or signs of sepsis were include in this study.

Results: Among 100 positive samples 60 (60%) were males (Table 1). The age wise distribution of the gender has been shown in the with maximum no. of culture positive samples in age 25-35 years (36%) followed by 35-45 (17 %) and then followed by 45-55 (16%) of age group respectively. The predominant bacterial isolates *S. aureus* (35%), *P. aeruginosa* (22%), *E. coli* (15%), *Proteus spp.* (7%), *K. aerogenes* (6%), *Streptococcus spp.* (5%) and one fungal isolate *C. albicans* (10%).

Conclusion: It has been concluded that wound infections in this were polymicrobial in nature and, in most cases, associated with *S. aureus*, *E.coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. A continuous inspection should be carried out to monitor the susceptibility of these pathogens and chose appropriate regimens both for prophylaxis and treatment of surgical wound infections.

Keywords: Aerobes, *Candida Albicans*, Post-Operative Wounds, Infections.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Despite an improved understanding of the pathophysiology, methods of prevention and prophylaxis and technological advances that have been made in surgery and wound management, surgical wound infections remain the most common cause of post-operative morbidity and mortality. [1] A surgical wound may get infected by

the exogenous bacterial flora which may be present in the environmental air of the operation theatre or by the endogenous flora. [2] Surgical wound infection remains one of the most important post-operative complications, accounting for 10 to 20% of the hospital costs. Although total elimination is not possible, a

reduction in the infection rate to a minimal level could have significant benefits in terms of both the patient comfort and the medical resources which are used. [3] The rate of infection of the surgical wounds is influenced by the duration of the pre-operative hospitalization, administration of the prophylactic antibiotics, the duration of the surgery and by the fact as to whether the surgery was emergency or elective. Patient factors and environmental factors, both local and general, like age and nutritional status and pre-existing illnesses also determine the final outcome. Postoperative wound infection can occur from first day onwards to many years after an operation but commonly occurs between the fifth and tenth days after surgery. [4] It may originate during the operation i.e. as a primary wound infection or may occur after the operation from sources in the ward or as a result of some complications i.e. secondary wound infection. [5,6] and can be characterized by various combinations of the signs of infection (e.g. pain, tenderness, warmth, erythema, swelling, drainage).⁴ Most post-operative wound infections are hospital acquired and vary from one hospital to the other and even within a given hospitals and they are associated with increased morbidity and mortality.⁵ The site of infection may be limited to the suture line or may become extensive in the operative site and the infecting microorganisms are variable, depending on the type and location of surgery, and antimicrobials. Surgical site infections (SSIs) which account 17% of all health care-associated infections are the second most common HAIs next to urinary tract infections. They occur after approximately 3% of all operations and result in greater lengths of stay and additional costs.⁶ The emergence of poly antimicrobial resistant strains of hospital pathogens has also presented a challenge in the provision of good quality inpatient care. [7] The battle between

bacteria and their susceptibility to drugs is yet problematic among public, researchers, clinicians and drug companies who are looking for effective drugs. [8]

The aim of the study was to isolate aerobic bacterial and fungal infections from post-operative wounds, establish the antimicrobial susceptibility pattern of isolated bacterial agents and proffer ways and means for the prevention of post-operative wound infections.

Materials and Methods

The study was a cross sectional study which was carried in the Department of Microbiology, Netaji Subhas Medical College and Hospital, Bihta, Bihar, India for one year. Out of 210 samples, 100 samples were culture positive (47.61%). Total 100 patients with post-operative wound infection either sex or any age, who had surgical wound pus, discharge, or signs of sepsis were include in this study. Patients with cellulitis and suture abscess were excluded from this study.

Using sterile cotton swabs, two pus swabs/wound swabs were collected aseptically from each patient suspected of having post-operative wound infection. Gram stained preparations were made from one swab for provisional diagnosis. The other swab was inoculated on nutrient agar, 5% sheep blood agar (BA) and MacConkey agar (MA) plates and incubated at 37°C for 24-48 hours before being reported as sterile. Growth on culture plates was identified by its colony characters and the battery of standard biochemical tests. [9,10] All dehydrated media, reagents were procured from Laboratories

Statistical Analysis: Data was entered in Microsoft excel spreadsheet and analysed using appropriate statistical software application.

Results

Table 1: Sex and age distribution of Culture positive Patients

Gender	N	%
Male	60	60
Female	40	40
Age in years		
Below 25	24	24
25-35	36	36
35-45	17	17
45-55	16	16
55-65	14	14
Above 65	11	11

Among 100 positive samples 60 (60%) were males (Table 1). The age wise distribution of the gender has been shown in the with maximum no. of culture positive samples in age 25-35 years (36%) followed by 35-45 (17 %) and then followed by 45-55 (16%) of age group respectively.

Table 2: Distribution of Organisms Causing Surgical Site Infection

Organism	No. of isolates	%
Staphylococcus aureus	35	35
Pseudomonas aeruginosa	22	22
Escherichia coli	15	15
Klebsiella aerogenes	7	7
Proteus spp.	6	6
Streptococcus spp.	5	5
Candida albicans	10	10

The predominant bacterial isolates *S. aureus* (35%), *P. aeruginosa* (22%), *E. coli* (15%), *Proteus spp.* (7%), *K. aerogenes* (6%), *Streptococcus spp.* (5%) and one fungal isolate *C. albicans* (10%).

Table 3: Susceptibility pattern showing number (%) of the different bacterial isolates sensitive to various antimicrobial agents

Organisms (N)	CMX	AUG	CFX	CFL	AMP	GN	FX	CFE	ERY
No (%) of isolates sensitive to various antibiotics tested									
Staphylococcus aureus (35)	15	28	5	17	17	25	8	6	25
Pseudomonas aeruginosa (22)	4	13	8	4	5	17	2	7	2
Escherichia coli (15)	10	14	12	10	12	8	6	12	2
Klebsiella aerogenes (7)	2	4	4	2	5	7	4	4	2
Proteus spp. (6)	4	4	2	5	4	4	2	4	0
Streptococcus spp. (5)	0	0	0	5	5	5	0	5	5

The in vitro antimicrobial sensitivity studies showed that organisms react differently to various antibiotics, as demonstrated by their sensitivity patterns. None of the isolates scored less than 50% sensitivity to Augmentin and Gentamicin. It is likely that these antibiotics may not

have been misused or because the organisms may not have been frequently exposed to the antibiotics in this locality.

Discussion

Post-operative wound infections are major global problem in the field of surgery

leading to many complications, increased morbidity and mortality. [11,12] Most post-surgical wound infections are hospital acquired and vary from one hospital to the other. [13] Lack of standardized criteria for diagnosis presents a challenge to monitor the global epidemiology of surgical site infection. In addition to this, emerging of high anti-microbial resistance among bacterial pathogens has made the management and treatment of post-operative wound infections difficult. [14]

From a microbiological perspective, the primary function of normal, intact skin is to control microbial populations that live on the skin surface and to prevent underlying tissue from becoming colonized and invaded by potential pathogens. Exposure of subcutaneous tissue following a loss of skin integrity (i.e., a wound) provides a moist, warm, and nutritious environment that is conducive to microbial colonization and proliferation. However, the abundance and diversity of microorganisms in any wound will be influenced by factors such as wound type, depth, location, and quality, the level of tissue perfusion, and the antimicrobial efficacy of the host immune response. Out of 220 samples, 100 samples were culture positive (47.61%) whereas various other studies from India have shown the rate of SSI to vary from 6.1% to 38.7%. [15-18]

The predominant bacterial isolates *S. aureus* (35%), *P. aeruginosa* (22%), *E. coli* (15%), *Proteus spp.* (7%), *K. aerogenes* (6%), *Streptococcus spp.* (5%) and one fungal isolate *C. albicans* (10%). The relative high number of Enterobacteriaceae isolated in this study points to the fact that the presence of enteric organisms in the wounds at operation probably resulted to subsequent sepsis. Gorbath and Barlet (1974) reported similar findings. The findings therefore infer that enteric organisms are important determinants of healing in surgical wounds. [19] The high incidence of Gram-negative organisms,

especially *P. aeruginosa*, *E. coli*, *K. aerogenes* and *Proteus spp.*, confirms the observation that most wound infections arising from abdominal procedures are presently acquired from the patient's own faecal flora. Bhattacharyya and Kosloski (1990) and Okodua (1996) also reported similar findings. [20,21]

The high isolation of *S. aureus* (35.0%) agrees with the findings of earlier work carried out by Enweani et al. (2003). [22] The predominance of *S. aureus* is, however, not surprising as it forms the bulk of the normal flora of the skin and nails (Junet et al., 2004). [23] Although the individual immune status of subjects used for this study was not ascertained at any time during this study, the age ranges in which there were high rates of infected wounds may be due to a decline in immunological competence among people in such age groups. This is, however, at variance with the work of Olagoke (2004). [24,25]

Conclusion

The report provides a good picture of the pathogens that cause wound infections in this hospital. Wound infections in this study were polymicrobial in nature, with *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* being the most common bacteria found. The resistance of these pathogens should be monitored on a regular basis, and suitable regimens for both prophylaxis and treatment of surgical wound infections should be chosen. In order to avoid and monitor surgical wound infections at a low cost, regular communication between the microbiology department and the surgeons is highly advised. This will push the use of antimicrobial agents to be more realistic, and it will aid in the prevention of infections.

References

1. Lauwers S, De Smet F. Surgical site infections. *Acta Clinica Belgica*. 1998 Jan 1;53(5):303-10.

2. Culbertson WR, Altemeier WA, Gonzalez LL, Hill EO. Studies on the epidemiology of postoperative infection of clean operative wounds. *Annals of Surgery*. 1961 Oct;154 (4):599.
3. Haley RW, Schaberg DR, Crossley KB, Von Allmen SD, McGowan Jr JE. Extra charges and prolongation of stay attributable to nosocomial infections: a prospective interhospital comparison. *The American journal of medicine*. 1981 Jan 1;70(1):51-8.
4. Medical Disability Guidelines. Wound infection, postoperative. 2010.
5. Isibor JO, Oseni A, Eyaufe A, Osagie R, Turay A. Incidence of aerobic bacteria and *Candida albicans* in post-operative wound infections. *African journal of microbiology research*. 2008 Nov 1;2(11):288-91.
6. Napolitano LM. Perspectives in surgical infections: what does the future hold? *Surgical Infections*. 2010 Apr 1;11(2):111-23.
7. Kamat US, Ferreira AM, Savio R, Motghare DD. Antimicrobial resistance among nosocomial isolates in a teaching hospital in Goa. *Indian journal of community medicine: official publication of Indian Association of Preventive & Social Medicine*. 2008 Apr;33(2):89.
8. Biadlegne F, Abera B, Alem A, Anagaw B. Bacterial isolates from wound infection and their antimicrobial susceptibility pattern in Felege Hiwot referral Hospital Northwest Ethiopia. *Ethiopian Journal of Health Sciences*. 2009;19(3).
9. Mac Faddin JF. *Biochemical tests for identification of medical bacteria*. Williams & Wilkins Co.; 1976.
10. Forbes BA, Sahm DF, Weissfeld AS. *Bailey and Scott's Diagnostic Microbiology*. 10th ed. St. Louis, Missouri, USA: Mosby Inc.; 1998.
11. Anguzu JR, Olila D: Drug sensitivity patterns of bacterial isolates from septic post-operative wounds in a regional referral hospital in Uganda. *Afr Health Sci* 2007, 7(3):148–154.
12. Raza MS, Chander A, Ranabhat A: Antimicrobial susceptibility patterns of the bacterial isolates in post-operative wound infections in a tertiary care hospital, Kathmandu, Nepal. *OJMM* 2013, 3(3):159–163.
13. Isibor JO, Oseni A, Eyaufe A, Osagie R, Turay A. Incidence of aerobic bacteria and *Candida albicans* in post-operative wound infections. *African journal of microbiology research*. 2008 Nov 1;2(11):288-91.
14. Andhoga J, Macharia AG, Maikuma IR, Wanyonyi ZS, Ayumba BR, Kakai R: Aerobic pathogenic bacteria in post-operative wounds at Moi teaching and referral hospital. *East Afr Med J* 2002, 79(12):640–644.
15. Malik S, Gupta A, Singh KP, Agarwal J, Singh M. Antibiogram of aerobic bacterial isolates from post-operative wound infections at a tertiary care hospital in India. *Journal of Infectious Diseases and Antimicrobial Agents*. 2011 Jan;28(1):45-51.
16. Lilani SP, Jangale N, Chowdhary A, Daver GB. Surgical site infection in clean and clean-contaminated cases. *Indian J Med Microbiol*. 2005 ;23(4):249-52.
17. Khan A K A, Rashed MR, Banu G. A Study on the Usage Pattern of Antimicrobial Agents for the Prevention of Surgical Site Infections (SSIs) in a Tertiary Care Teaching Hospital. *J Clin Diagn Res*. 2013 ;7(4):671-4.
18. Chakarborty SP, Mahapatra SK, Bal M, Roy S. Isolation and identification of vancomycin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* from postoperative pus sample. *Al Ameen J Med Sci*. 2011; 4(2):152-68.
19. Gorbach SL, Barlett JG. Amoebic infections. *N. Engl. J. Med*. 1974; 290:1174-1184.

20. Bhattacharyya M, Kosloske AM. Post-operative wound infection in Pediatric patients. *J. Paed. Surg.*1990; 125-29.
21. Okodua M. Bacterial post-operative wound infections. An unpublished dissertation in the school of medical laboratory science U.C.H Ibadan.1996.
22. Enweani IB, Esumeh FI, Akpe RA, Taffeng MY, Isibor JO. Bacteria associated with post-operative wounds. *Jour. Contem. Issues.*2003; 1:183-88.
23. Junet SB, Geo FB, Stephen AM. *Candida albicans* in: Jawetz, Melnick and Adelberg's Medical Microbiology, 23rd ed. McGraw Hill Companies. 2004; 645
24. Olagoke O. Post-operative wound infections. An unpublished dissertation in the school of medical laboratory science U.C.1A Ibadan. 2004
25. Hernández P. C., Pinedo C. M., Rodríguez R. P., Higuera E. J., Peláez D. S., Camuñas Ángel F., & Fernández J. M. Coloduodenal fistula in right colorectal cancer: Case report and review of the literature. *Journal of Medical Research and Health Sciences.* 2021;4(1): 1135–1138.